

Strength and Stress Analysis of Adhesive Bonded Joints of Isotropic and Anisotropic Materials

Sadao Amijima*, Akira Yoshida* and Toru Fujii**

* Faculty of Engineering, Doshisha Univ., Kyoto Japan

** 4th Research Center, Technical Research and Development Inst.
Japan Defense Agency, Kanagawa Japan

This paper deals with the two dimensional stress analysis of an adhesive layer and adherends based on a finite element analysis considering the effect of the adhesive layer. Tensile tests of bonded joints were carried out to compare with the numerous theoretical results by the finite element method. Using double lap joints, to minimize the effect of bending, the strength of three types of adhesive bonded joints (steel and F.R.P.) is measured. An attempt to show that the strength obtained from tests can be related to that obtained by the numerical method, were carried out.

Introduction

Recently, adhesive bonded structures were brought into greater use in the industries of aircrafts, automobiles and vehicles. Correspondingly, many studies on the stress distribution in adhesive bonded joints have been carried out. However, most studies¹⁻⁵ were concerned with the analyses of the stress distribution perpendicular to the adhesive layer (ie., a one dimensional analysis along x direction or a two dimensional analysis but in x-z plane; Fig.1(a)) and no consideration is given to the effect of widths, and those studies can not explain the effect of the differences of widths of adherends as shown in Fig.1(b). Therefore, two dimensional and anisotropic characteristics must be considered for the bonded joints of composite materials. A two dimensional finite element analysis considering the effects of the adhesive layer and the width of the adherends was presented in an earlier paper⁶. Some numerical examples of stress analyses for isotropic bonded joints were also shown. This paper deals with the two dimensional stress analysis based on the finite element method(F.E.M.), which was applied to

Fig.1 Adhesive bonded joint configurations

calculate the stress distributions of adhesive bonded joints not only for isotropic materials but also for anisotropic ones. The strength of bonded joints using steel (as isotropic materials) and F.R.P. (as anisotropic ones) adherends, were measured. An attempt to show that the strength obtained from the tests could be related to the numerical results, was carried out.

Finite Element Analysis

The numerical analysis procedure based on F.E.M. considering the effect of the adhesive layer is explained as follows. But, only the brief description is shown here because the details are given in reference [6].

Consider the adhesive bonded joints which consist of three parts (Fig. 2). Two dimensional stress components acting on an element are shown in Fig.3.

Fig.2 Adhesive bonded structure model

Fig.3 Two dimensional stress components

Fig.4 Triangular finite element

In our analysis, it is assumed that the stress along z direction in each adherend is constant and the adhesive layer is subjected to only pure deformations. Therefore, the bending effect is neglected.

The bond shearing stresses $\tau_x^{(a)}$ and $\tau_y^{(a)}$ are defined by the relative displacements between upper and lower adherends, a rigidity G and thickness H of the adhesive layer.

$$\tau_x^{(a)} = G \frac{u^{(1)} - u^{(2)}}{H} \quad \tau_y^{(a)} = G \frac{v^{(1)} - v^{(2)}}{H} \quad (1)$$

For the finite element procedure, the adhesive bonded region is divided into double triangular finite elements having six nodal points shown in Fig. 4. The hypotheses that internal displacements in the finite element are interpolated linearly by each nodal point and the energy stored in the adhesive layer is involved into the total potential energy, give the following finite equilibrium equation.

$$([k^{(1)}] + [k^{(2)}] + [k^{(a)}])\{d\} = \{f\} \quad (2)$$

where, $\{d\}$ and $\{f\}$ are the vector of nodal displacements and external forces, and $[k^{(1)}]$ and $[k^{(2)}]$ are stiffness matrices of each adherend. They are similar to the stiffness matrix for two dimensional plane stress problems. $[k^{(a)}]$ also stiffness matrix but it is derived from the adhesive layer. Table 1 shows the material constants used for the calculation of stress distributions.

Table 1. Properties of the adherend and adhesive

Type of joint	Adherend	Adhesive
Aluminium joint	E = 7000 (kg/mm ²) v = 0.33	G = 100 (kg/mm ²) H = 0.1 (mm)
Steel joint	E = 20000 (kg/mm ²) v = 0.30	
F.R.P.(P) joint	E _x = E _y = 1750 (kg/mm ²) v _x = v _y = 0.13 G _{xy} = 330 (kg/mm ²)	
F.R.P.(R) joint	E _x = 2300 (kg/mm ²) E _y = 740 (kg/mm ²) v _x = 0.31 v _y = 0.10 G _{xy} = 220 (kg/mm ²)	

Experiments

Three kinds of adhesive bonded joints whose materials of adherends are different, were tested at room temperature. The strength of the joints were measured by the testing method for strength properties of adhesives in shear by tension loading using Instrone type testing machine of 5mm/min. cross head speed. In order to minimize the effect of bending, double lap joint specimens shown in Fig.5 were used. Specimens are divided into three groups by their materials of adherends, steel joints, F.R.P.(P) joints and F.R.P.(R) joints.

- (1) Steel joint - - - - Rolled spread steel at high temperature was used. Dimensions of the specimen are shown in Fig.6 and 7.
- (2) F.R.P. joint- - - - The F.R.P. double lap joint embodied by two single lap joints bonded back to back, are used.

Fig. 5 Notation of double lap joints

Fig. 6 Dimensions of the steel joint specimen ($B=\text{const.}$)

Fig. 7 Dimensions of the steel joint specimen ($B_1 \neq B_2$)

Fig.8 Dimensions of the F.R.P. joint specimen ($B=\text{const.}$)

- Dimensions of the specimen are shown in Fig.8.
- F.R.P.(P) joint..... Plain woven glass cloth reinforced polyester plates were used as adherends. Fiber orientation angle θ between the main fiber direction and the direction of the applied load is zero.
- F.R.P.(R) joint..... Roving glass fiber reinforced polyester plates were used as adherends. θ is also zero. They are one of unidirectional composites.

The bonded surfaces of all adherends had been sandpapered perpendicular to the direction of applied load and cleaned by acetone before they were bonded. All specimens were bonded for two hours at 80°C in an oven under 0.1kg/cm^2 pressure. Araldite AW106 and HV953U hardener were used as the adhesive. Mixture ratio of AW106 to HV953U is 10:8 in weight content.

Results and Discussion

Two dimensional stress distributions

For the two dimensional stress analysis by F.E.M., the bonded joint model was divided into triangular elements as shown in Fig.9. Some examples of numerical results for the joint with different widths of adherends are given in Fig.10 to 12. Fig.10 shows the bond shearing stress distributions ($\tau^{(a)}/\tau_{\text{mean}}^{(a)}$) in the adhesive layer, where $\tau_{\text{mean}}^{(a)}$ is the average bond shearing stress as the quotient derived from the load divided by the bonded area. The bond shearing stress is not distributed uniformly and that distribution is more complex than in one dimensional problems.

The bond shearing stress distributions along the line $Y=0$ and $Y=B$ (parallel to the longitudinal direction) are shown in Fig.11. In this case, those distributions are not symmetrical with respect to the line $X/L=0.5$ and the maximum bond shearing stress occurs at one corner of $X=0$ and $Y=B$. But, in the case where both widths of adherends are the same, the bond shearing distribution is symmetrical.

Fig.12 shows the axial stress distribution (σ_x/σ_0) in the wide adherend, i.e., equal lines of the nondimensional axial stress. It is found that a sudden change of the axial stress occurred at the interface between the bonded and unbonded regions..

The differences of two dimensional stress distributions between isotropic and anisotropic adherends are shown in Fig.13 and 14. In these cases,

Fig.9 Finite element division for the two dimensional analysis

Fig.10 Two dimensional bond shearing stress distributions (Aluminum joint; $L=20\text{mm}$, $2B_1=40\text{mm}$, $2B_2=25\text{mm}$)

Fig.11 Bond shearing distributions (Aluminum; $L=20\text{mm}$, $2B_1=40\text{mm}$, $2B_2=25\text{mm}$)

Fig.12 Equal lines of axial stresses in the wide adherend Aluminum joint; $L=20\text{mm}$, $2B_1=40\text{mm}$, $2B_2=25\text{mm}$)

the width of each adherend is the same (see Fig.1(a)). Fig.13(a) and (b) show the bond shearing stress distribution along the center line ($Y=0$) and the periphery ($Y=B$) of the F.R.P.(P) and F.R.P.(R) joints, respectively. Dotted lines in the figures show the one dimensional theoretical results. Dissimilar to the previous case ($B_1 \neq B_2$), however, little differences between the bond shearing stress along the center line and the periphery are found. The numerical results almost coincide with the one dimensional theoretical results. However, in the case of the Aluminium joint, a relatively large difference can be found as shown in Fig.13(c). This difference of the bond shearing stress is derived from the effect of Poisson's ratio. In general,

(a) F.R.P.(P) joint

(b) F.R.P.(R) joint

(c) Aluminum joint

Fig.13 Bond shearing stress distribution by F.E.M. and the one dimensional analysis, ($L=20\text{mm}$, $B=12.5\text{mm}$)

(a) F.R.P.(P) joint

(b) F.R.P.(R) joint

(c) Aluminum joint

Fig.14 Axial stress distribution of the adherend in x-direction by F.E.M. and the one dimensional analysis ($L=20\text{mm}$, $B=12.5\text{mm}$)

all materials transversely shrink when an unidirectional loading is applied to them. The shrinkage at the periphery is larger than that near the center. The shrinkage makes the transverse relative displacement and the resultant bond shearing stress perpendicular to the longitudinal axis occurs. This shearing stress makes the difference of the bond shearing stress distribution along the center line and the periphery. This difference depends not only on the geometry of joints but also on Poisson's ratio of the adherends because the transverse shrinkage is proportional to Poisson's ratio. Especially, for the F.R.P.(P) joint, the transverse Poisson's ratio ν_x is much smaller than others ($\nu_x=0.13$). The effect of the width of adherends is less than others. For the F.R.P.(R) joint, however, the effect of the width is as large as the Aluminum joint because the transverse Poisson's ratio ν_x is not as small as the F.R.P.(P), although the F.R.P.(R) adherend has anisotropic properties and a small Poisson's ratio in the longitudinal direction as well as the F.R.P.(P). More distinct difference among these three kinds of joints can be seen in Fig.14. These figures show the axial stress distributions along the center line and the periphery.

Fig.15 shows the relation between the maximum bond shearing stress concentration ($\tau_{max}^{(a)}/\tau_{mean}^{(a)}$) and the width of the adherend, where each width of the adherends is the same. It is found that the F.R.P.(P) joint has less sensitivities of the width on the maximum bond shearing stress concentration than others.

(a) F.R.P. joints

(b) Aluminum joint

Fig.15 Relation between the maximum bond shearing stress concentration and the width of adherends (L=20mm)

Test results

The tensile test results are considered under the following assumptions.

- (1) The final fracture of the bonded joint in shear is caused by the adhesive fracture or the delamination in the interface between the adhesive and the adherend.
- (2) The adherend and the adhesive still remain in the elastic state at the fracture occurrence
- (3) The fracture occurs when the maximum bond shearing stress $\tau_{max}^{(a)}$ in the

adhesive layer becomes equal to the value τ_A (the shear strength of the adhesive or the bonding strength in shear).

From the assumption (3), the strength τ_B of the joint is defined.

$$\tau_B = \frac{P_{\max}(\text{Maximum tensile load})}{A \text{ (Bonded area)}} = \frac{P_{\max}}{2BL} = \frac{\tau_A}{\left(\frac{\tau_{\max}^{(a)}}{\tau_{\text{mean}}^{(a)}}\right)} \quad (3)$$

☆ for double lap joints

It is difficult to obtain reliable values of τ_A , G and H actually by experiments. However, τ_A can be estimated from some experiments and try and error calculations using F.E.M. stress analysis according to the following procedure.

- (a) When the width of the bonded joints is narrow and constant, the relation between the lap length and the strength should be obtained at first from tensile tests (See Fig.16). Two experimental points must be plotted at least.
- (b) Measure the dimensions and material constants of the tested specimens except G and H. Then, calculate the relation between a joint constant C which includes G and H, and the maximum bond shearing stress concentration for each lap length by F.E.M. (See Fig.17). The joint constant C is defined as follow.

$$C^2 = \frac{G}{EH} \left(\frac{1}{T_1} + \frac{1}{T_2} \right) \quad (4)$$

where, T_1 and T_2 are the thickness of the adherend 1 and 2, respectively.

- (c) From Fig.16 and 17, find the joint constant x which satisfies the following relation

$$\frac{\tau_{B1}}{\tau_{B2}} = \frac{y_2}{y_1} \quad (5)$$

Fig.16 A typical relation between the strength and the lap length ($B=\text{const.}$)

Fig.17 A typical relation between the joint constant and the max. bond shearing stress concentration ($B=\text{const.}$)

- (d) Substitute the shear strength τ_B and τ_{max}/τ_{mean} (calculated by F.E.M. using the joint constant x) into equation (3). Then, τ_A can be obtained. However, the suitable value of τ_A which approximately satisfies the experimental results (the relation between the strength and the lap length) must be found by try and error calculations.

In the case of same bonding conditions, the strengths of other bonded joints can be analyzed if τ_A is estimated.

Fig.18 The relation between the strength and the lap length (Steel joint; $B=B_1=B_2=12.5$ mm)

Fig.19 The relation between the max. bond shearing stress concentration and the joint constant (Steel joint; $B=B_1=B_2=12.5$ mm)

Fig.18 shows the test results of steel joints with $2B=25$ mm. Fig.19 shows the relation between the maximum bond shearing stress concentration and the joint constant for the steel joint. From these figures, the suitable value τ_A is estimated as 2.8 kg/mm^2 . The solid line in Fig.18, which approximately satisfied the test results, was calculated by F.E.M..

Fig.20 shows the comparisons between experimental results and numerical results for the steel joint. Except the case of wide steel joints, calculated results relatively agree with the experimental results (Fig.20(a)). It is considered that the lower strength than the expected value is affected by twist moments acting in the x-y plane. For the wide bonded joints, it is difficult to apply the tensile load uniformly on them.

Tensile test results of the F.R.P. bonded joints are shown in Fig.21 and 22. In order to calculate the strength of the F.R.P. joints, $\tau_A=2.8 \text{ kg/mm}^2$ is used, but it is not proper because its value is for the steel joint. Calculated strengths of the F.R.P. joint (both F.R.P.) are always higher than those obtained by experiments. These discrepancies are not induced from the value $\tau_A=2.8 \text{ kg/mm}^2$, but from the fracture mode of F.R.P. bonded joints. Namely, the inter-laminar delaminations of the F.R.P. adherends took place at the fracture of the F.R.P. joints as shown in Photo.1. The inter-laminar

(a) The width of each adherend is the same

(b) The width of each adherend is different

Fig.20 Comparisons between the experimental results and calculated ones with respect to the strength of the steel joint (the lap length is constant, $L=10\text{mm}$)

(a) The width of each adherend is the same and constant ($B=12.5\text{mm}$)

(b) The width of each adherend is the same but it varies ($L=10\text{mm}$)

Fig.21 Comparisons between the experimental results and calculated ones with respect to the strength of the F.R.P.(P) joint

(a) The width of each adherend is the same and constant ($B=12.5\text{mm}$)

(b) The width of each adherend is the same but it varies ($L=10\text{mm}$)

Fig.22 Comparisons between the experimental results and calculated ones with respect to the strength of the F.R.P.(R) joint

Photo.1 Failed specimens of F.R.P.(P) joints ($L=10\text{mm}$; $2B=12.5, 25.0, 37.5, 50.0\text{mm}$)

delamination strength of the F.R.P. is lower than the adhesive strength τ_A .

Conclusions

The results obtained in this study are summarized as follows;

- (1) The stress distribution in adherends and the bond shearing stress distribution are not constant in the direction of width.
- (2) The width and anisotropic properties of adherends affect the two dimensional stress distributions of adhesive bonded joints.
- (3) These stress distributions become to suffer the effect of the width of adherends more stronger at the higher value of Poisson's ratio of adherends in tension.
- (4) The analysis of bonded joints by the finite element method presented in this paper would be available in design if the fracture of bonded joints occurs at the boundary between the adhesive and the adherend.

References

1. Goland, M. and Reissner, E., "The stresses in Cemented Joints," J.Appl. Mech., vol.1, 1944, pp. A-17
2. Szepe, F., "Strength of Adhesive-bonded Lap Joint with Respect to Change of Temperature and Fatigue," Experimental Mechanics, vol.16 No.5, 1966, pp. 280
3. Wooley, G. R. and Carver, D. R., "Stress Concentration Factors for Bonded Lap Joints," J.Aircraft, vol.8, No.10, 1971, pp. 817
4. Erdogan, F. and Ratwani, M., "Stress Distribution in Bonded Joints," J. Composite Materials, vol.5, 1971, pp.378
5. Barker, R. M. and Hatt, F., "Analysis of Bonded Joints in Vehicular Structures," AIAA journal, vol.11, No.12, 1973, pp. 1650
6. Amijima, S., Fujii, T. and Yoshida, A. "Two Dimensional Stress Analysis on Adhesive Bonded Joints," Proceedings of The 20th Japan Congress on Materials Research, 1977, Japan